

Land Use Transformations Project (JHI-C3-1)
Deliverable D3 – Opportunity and Risk Mapping – Story Maps
Internal Note

Versions, first complete 28/2/2024

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.15066267

This deliverable was the preparation of Story Mapping and/or Infographic Summary of Milestones (M18-20). The story maps are collated at [Land Use Transformations](#), with [Climatic Water Balance](#), [Updating Land Capability for Agriculture](#) and [Updating Peatland Condition Mapping](#).

The James Hutton Institute is supported by the Scottish Government's Rural and Environment Science and Analytical Services Division (RESAS). Research funded through grant JHI-C3-1 and previous Strategic Research Programmes.

